

GREEN HUMAN RESOURCE PRACTICE AND ITS EFFECTS ON ORGANIZATIONAL SUSTAINABILITY WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO COLLEGES IN CHITTOOR DISTRICT, ANDHRA PRADESH

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Abstract

Green human resource management becomes important to provide environmentally friendly products and operations, manage corporate environmental programmes successfully and to overcome implementation challenges of corporate environmental programs. This study examined the influence of green human resource practices on organizational sustainability of colleges in Chittoor District, Andhra Pradesh. Descriptive research design is applied in this research. Green HRM practices such as green employee discipline, green health and safety, green employee relations, green orientation, green performance evaluation, green reward management have been considered as independent variables. Organizational sustainability such as institution use of environmental friendly products, establishing partnership to protect environment, reducing environmental accident in the institution, purchase non-renewable materials and waste management have been taken as dependent variables. For these variables, questionnaire constructed based on previous authors tools. After constructing the questionnaire, it is distributed to the faculty members working in colleges, Chittoor District, Andhra Pradesh. A sample of 150 faculty members approached to participate in this survey through convenience sampling method. The collected data have been entered into SPSS packages for further analysis. Frequency analysis has been used to know the number of participants belonging to which category; regression analysis is used to know the influence of green human resource management practices on organizational sustainability. The result revealed that green human resource management practices have positively influenced the organizational sustainability.

Keywords: Green Human Resource Practices, Organizational Sustainability Colleges and Faculty Members

1. INTRODUCTION

Green HRM is referred to all the activities involved for development, implement and maintenance of a system that aims to making the employees for green organization. From the human resource management point, green is concerned with transforming normal employees into green employees in order to achieve environmental goals of the organization and provide significant contribution to environmental sustainability. It refers to the policies, practices and systems that make employees of the organization green for the benefit of the individual, society, natural environment and the business (Parul Deshwal, 2015). Greening is essential to avoid or minimize global warming, natural disasters such as Acid rains, red rains, Tsunamis, flooding, hurricanes, droughts etc owing to informal, harmful and greedy usage of natural resources for production and consumption, health diseases owing to pollution and harms to animals and other natural creatures, green ensure the appropriate balance of relationships among plants, animals, people, and their environment. It is essential for the survival of humans and business

organizations for a prolonged period of time. Certo and Certo (2008) stated that corporate social responsibility is the managerial obligation to take action that protects and improves both the welfare of society and the organization. Every organization perform corporate environmental management as compulsory. Therefore, there are environmental goals to be achieved by the organization.

Green human resource management is important not only at the organizational level but also at the employee or individual level. Employees have private life in addition to work life and therefore they are employees at the work life domain and consumers at the private life domain. Environmentally friendly behaviour in both life domains is facilitated. Greening will be beneficial for the employee to give a significant individual contribution for a successful corporate management and to become a good citizen giving a significant contribution to environmental sustainability (Jackson, et. al., 2011). In order to achieve organizational environmental goal, four green human resources are required namely, i.e. green competencies, green attitude, green behaviours and green results. Employees should possess a sufficient amount of knowledge and skills in respect of greening. Employee needs to have a right attitude of greening. Right attitude means appropriate beliefs (cognitive), feelings (affective) and intention to behave (behavioural) with regard to greening (Opatha and Arton Arulrajan, 2014).

Green results are outcomes, which is environmentally friendly. Green results are defined as the employee has produced green outcomes. Green innovations are such as new environmental initiatives, new solutions for waste reduction, pollution reduction, etc. Green outcomes are such as, number of hours of working with natural light or minimum number of electricity bulbs, amount of reduction of electricity consumption, amount of reduction of existing level of inputs wastage, and degree of achievement of specific environmental performance targets.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Monicah Wanjiku Kuna (2019) revealed that during recruitment and selection, the management seeks to recruit staff and personnel that are conversant and ready to apply their skills and expertise to better the ecological surrounding. Employees recruited are not only left on their own to work out the plan, but are also coached and trained on their specific matters and issues that relate to the environment. Motivation of the staff had a higher relationship compared to the other variables.

Maeen Uddin (2018) found that there is a strong tie between human resource management and organizational environmental performance. It is also found that, the adoption of green practices has a positive relationship with increased organizational performance and helps to promote the organization image. Lenny Christina Nawangsari and Achmad Hidayat Sutawidjaya (2018). It is found that small and medium-sized enterprises can make themselves greener by making strategic and organizational change because with eco-friendly, innovation and creativity, human resources and cost savings. Anuradhaa and Srivastava (2018) reviewed the negative and positive impacts of green practices on employees health and the employees commitment. It is found that most of the authors said that green human recourse practices have positive impacts on employees health and commitment. Ahmed Hassan (2018) found that the level of

implementation of green practices was moderate in all dimensions of green practices. It is also showed that the majority of restaurants care about implementing energy conservation practices. Farheen Javed (2017) found that selection, recruitment, training and development, performance appraisal and compensation were the variables positively associated with organization outcome. It further examined the effect of independent variable on organizational outcome. It is found that selection training and development are having significant effect on organizational outcomes. Brefo-Manuh, et. al., (2017) found that both public and private sector organizations use green performance appraisal system to improve employees' performance, train and motivate employees, among others. However, use of green performance appraisal system in private organizations was greater than in public organizations. It is indicated that green performance appraisal system positively and significantly predicted organizational effectiveness.

3. RESEARCH PROBLEM

There is an argument that the support of top management, environment training and development, team work, employees' empowerment and reward system are the essence for carrying out environment management activities successfully (Daily and Huang, 2001). Employees involvement and participation can be encouraged within to seek entrepreneur within the business organization, who are socially or ecologically oriented known as eco entrepreneur. The green human resource management practices will become important driver for environment sustainability within the organization by aligning its practices and policies with organizational sustainability goal reflecting towards eco-focus (Jain, 2015). Hence, how these activities are implemented in the organization is analysed in this research.

4. RESEARCH FRAMEWORK FOR THIS STUDY

5. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This research paper examined the faculty members opinion towards green HRM practices and organizational sustainability in their college at Chittoor District, Andhra Pradesh. And also it examined the influence of green HRM practices on organisational sustainability.

6. HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

Green HRM practices of green employee discipline, green health and safety, green employees relation, green orientation, green performance evaluation and green reward management have been influenced the organizational sustainability.

7. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research methodology is a careful investigation about the research problem especially through search for new facts in any branch of knowledge.

Type of Research

This study analyses the employees perception towards the implementation of green HRM practices for organizational sustainability in the colleges. Hence descriptive research is applied.

Sample Size

This study population includes the faculty members working in colleges of Chittoor District. Here the top 10 colleges as per NIRF ranking have been considered. There are around 580 faculty members working in these colleges. So the population for this is 580. Out of 580, 150 faculty members have been approached to participate in this survey through convenient sampling method. Then the questionnaire has been distributed.

Questionnaire Description

In this study, GHRM practices have been analysed with six dimensions namely green employee discipline, green health and safety, green employee relation, green orientation, green performance evaluation and green reward management. These are taken as independent variables. Organisational sustainability is considered as dependent variable. The questionnaire has been constructed based on previous authors studies.

Statistical Tools Applied

In order to answer the research objective and test the hypothesis regression analysis have been applied.

8. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The objective of the study is to analyse the effect of green human resource practices on organizational sustainability of the colleges. In order answer this objective, multiple linear regression analysis is executed. The results are discussed below.

Fig 1: Influence of GHRM Practices on the Use of Environmental Friendly Products in the College

Fig. – 1 explains the influence of GHRM practices on the use of environmental products in the colleges. It is hypothesized that GHRM practices have influencing the use of environmental friendly products in the college.

In order to examine the above stated hypothesis, regression analysis is applied. Here, green employee discipline, green health and safety, green employee relations, green orientation, green performance evaluation, green reward management practices have been considered as independent variables. Usage of the environment friendly product in the colleges is taken as dependent variable.

In the regression model summary, the adjusted r-square value is found to be 0.770. The corresponding p-value is 0.001, which is significant at one percent level. Hence, the stated hypothesis is accepted. It is found that the independent variables are significantly influencing the use of environment friendly products at 77.0 percent level in the colleges. The unstandardized co-efficient beta values indicate the strength of relationship between independent and dependent variables. It is presented by the equation as follows;

$$\text{Using environment friendly product} = 1.334 + 0.309 (\text{green discipline}) + 0.125 (\text{green orientation}) + 0.087 (\text{green performance evaluation}) - 0.123 (\text{green health and safety}) - 0.257 (\text{green reward}) - 0.464 (\text{green employee relations}).$$

From the regression equation, it is observed that green discipline, green performance evaluation and green orientation are positively and significantly influencing the institution to use environment friendly products. However, green health and safety management, green employee relations and green rewards are significantly and negatively influencing the colleges to use environmentally friendly products. From the unstandardized beta value, it is inferred that to have one unit increase of the colleges using the environment friendly products, there is a

increase of green discipline at 0.309 unit level, green orientation at 0.128 unit level, and green performance evaluation at 0.087 unit level. Similarly, to have one unit decrease of the firm using environmentally product, there is a decrease of green health and safety management at 0.123 level, green employee relation at 0.464 level and green reward 0.257 level. It is revealed that the green human resource practices have influenced the colleges to use environment friendly products or services.

Fig 2: Influence of GHRM Practices on the Establish Partnership with others for Green Environment in Colleges

Fig. 2 shows the influence of GHRM practices on the establish partnership with others for green environment in colleges. It is hypothesized that GHRM practices have influencing the establishing partnership with others for green environment in colleges. Further, regression analysis is applied to examine the above stated hypothesis. Here, green employee discipline, green health and safety, green employee relations, green orientation, green performance evaluation and green reward management practices have been considered as independent variables. Institution establishing partnership for green environment is taken as a dependent variable. In the regression model summary, the adjusted r-square value is found to be 0.822. The corresponding p-value is 0.001, which is significant at one percent level. Hence, the stated hypothesis is accepted at one percent level. So, green human resource practices are significantly influencing the firm to establish partnership for green environment at 82 percent level. Further, the unstandardized co-efficient beta values indicate the strength of relationship between dependent and independent variables. It is explained by the following equation as follows;

$$\text{Establishing partnership for green environment} = -0.310 + 0.365 (\text{green employee discipline}) + 0.332 (\text{green reward}) + 0.255 (\text{green health and safety}) + 0.179 (\text{green orientation}) - 0.307 (\text{green employee relation}) - 0.164 (\text{green performance evaluation}).$$

From the regression equation, it is noted that green employees discipline, green reward, green health and safety and green orientation are positively and significantly influenced the colleges to establish partnership for green environment. Green employee relation and green performance evaluation has negatively and significantly influenced the colleges to establish green environment. The unstandardized beta values indicated that to have increase of one unit in the colleges establishing partnership for green environment, green discipline is influenced at 0.365 level, green reward at 0.332 unit level and green health and safety at 0.255 unit level, green orientation at 0.139 unit level when other factors remain constant. To have one unit decrease of the colleges establishing for green environment, there is a decrease of green employee relation at -0.307 unit level and green performance evaluation at -0.164 levels.

Fig 3: Influence of GHRM Practices on Reduction of Environmental Accidents in Colleges

Fig. 3 indicates the influence of GHRM practices on reduction of environmental accidents in colleges. It is hypothesized that GHRM practices have influencing the reduction of environmental accidents in colleges. To test the above stated hypothesis, regression analysis is employed. Green human resource practices are taken as the independent variables and the colleges reducing the environmental accident is treated as the dependent variable.

In the regression model summary, the adjusted r-square value is found to be 0.747. The corresponding p-value is 0.001, which is significant at one percent level. Hence, the stated hypothesis is rejected. It is found that the independent variables are significantly influencing the colleges reducing the environmental accidents, spills and releases at 74.7 percent level. The unstandardized co-efficient beta values indicate the strength of relationship between independent and dependent variables. It is presented by the following equation.

$$\text{Reduction of environmental accidents} = 0.769 + 0.616 (\text{green employee discipline}) + 0.593 (\text{green reward}) - 0.172 (\text{green health and safety}) - 0.216 (\text{green orientation}) - 0.396 (\text{green employee relations}).$$

From the regression equation, it is explained that green employees discipline, green reward are having positive impact on the colleges reducing the environmental accidents. However, green health and safety, green orientation and green employee relation are negatively influencing the reduction of environmental accidents in colleges. From the unstandardized beta co-efficient value, it is inferred that, the increase of 0.616 green employee discipline and 0.593 units increase in green reward, there is increase of one unit for the environmental accidents, spills and releases in colleges. For every decrease of 0.142 unit of green job design analysis, there is decrease of one unit for the firm environmental accidents. Similarly green health and safety, orientation and green employees relation are decreased at 0.172, 0.216 and 0.396 units respectively, which leads to one unit decrease of the firm environmental accidents in the colleges while other factors remain constant. It is explained that green employees discipline and green reward are having positive effect on the colleges to reduce the environmental accidents. But, green health and safety, green orientation and green employee relations are having negative effect on the colleges to reduce the environmental accidents.

Fig 4: Influence of GHRM Practices on Purchase of non-renewable products in colleges

Fig. 4 explains the influence of GHRM practices on purchase of non-renewable products in colleges. It is hypothesized that GHRM products have been influencing the purchase of non-renewable products in colleges. In order to examine the above stated hypothesis, regression analysis is applied. Green human resource practices are considered as independent variables and purchase of non-renewable materials, chemicals, and components is taken as a dependent variable.

In the regression model summary, the adjusted r-square value is found to be 0.221. The corresponding p-value is 0.001, which is significant at one percent level. So, the stated hypothesis is accepted. Green human resource practices are significantly influencing the purchase of green environmental product in colleges at 22.1 percent level. The unstandardized

co-efficient beta values indicate the strength of relationship between independent and dependent variables. It is presented by the equation as follows;

$$\text{Purchase of non-renewable products} = -0.248 + 1.123 (\text{green health and safety}) + 1.016 (\text{green performance evaluation}) + 0.802 (\text{green employee discipline}) - 0.127 (\text{green employee relation}) - 0.072 (\text{green orientation}).$$

From the regression equation, it is explained that green employee discipline, green health and safety, green performance evaluation have positively and significantly influenced the colleges to purchase the non-renewable products. Green employee relation and green orientation have negatively and significantly influenced the colleges to purchase the non-renewable products. From the unstandardised co-efficient beta value, it is revealed that to have one unit increase in the purchase of the non-renewable products in the colleges, green health and safety is influenced at 1.123 level, when remain other factors constant, followed by green performance evaluation at 0.016 level and green employee discipline at 0.802 level. But the decrease of green employee relation at 0.127 level and green orientation at 0.072 unit level leads to decrease of one unit in the purchase of non-renewable products in the colleges. It is inferred that green health and safety, green employees and discipline have positively influenced the purchase of non-renewable materials in the colleges. But, green employee relation and green orientation have negatively influenced the colleges in the purchase of non-renewable materials.

Fig 5: Influence of GHRM Practices on Waste Management in colleges

Fig. 5 indicates the influence of GHRM practices on waste management practices in the colleges. It is hypothesized that GHRM practices have influencing the waste management practices in the colleges. Here, green employee discipline, green health and safety, green employee relations, green orientation, green performance evaluation, green reward have been considered as independent variables and waste management in colleges is treated as dependent variable.

Regression analysis is applied to know the influence of green human resource management practices on the reduction of wastes in the colleges. In the regression model summary, the adjusted r-square value is found to be 0.780. The corresponding p-value is found to be 0.001, which is significant at one percent level. Hence, the stated hypothesis gets accepted. It is explained that the independent variables are influenced at 78.0 percent towards the reduction of wastes. Hence, it is inferred that the green human resource management practices have been influencing the colleges to reduce the waste. The unstandardized co-efficient beta values indicate the strength of relationship between the independent and dependent variables. It is presented by the equation as follows;

$$\text{Waste management in colleges} = 1.288 + 0.020 (\text{green health and safety}) + 0.436 (\text{green reward}) + 0.085 (\text{green environmental orientation}) - 0.382 (\text{green employee relations}) - 0.087 (\text{green performance evaluation}).$$

From the regression equation, it is observed that green health and safety, green orientation and green reward have positively and significantly influenced the colleges performance of reducing the waste. But, green employee relation and green performance evaluation have negatively influenced the colleges performance relating to waste. From the unstandardized co-efficient beta value, for every increase of 0.020 units in green health and safety, the outcome of regression equation showed that there is an increase of one unit in reduction of waste. Similarly, increase of 0.436 units in green reward leads to one unit increase of colleges to reduce the waste. For increase of 0.085 units in green orientation, there is one unit increase of reducing the waste in colleges. For every decrease of 0.132 units in green employee relation and green performance evaluation, the result of regression showed that there is decrease of one unit in reduction of waste in the institution.

9. FINDINGS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

It is found that the green discipline, green performance evaluation and green orientation are positively influencing the usage of environmental friendly products at colleges. But green health and safety green employee relation have negatively influenced the usage of environmental friendly products at colleges. So the institution may follow the environmental compliance and auditing programs effectively. And the institution may create green zone strategies to prevent various health problems of the employees.

It is found that the green employee discipline, green reward and green health and safety have positively influenced the establishment of partnership for green environment. But the green employee relation and green performance evaluation have negative influence on establishment of partnership for green environment. So the institution may provide training to faculty members in environmental management and the institution may evaluate the individuals green performance as a part of the overall performance assessment.

It is found that the green employees discipline and green reward are having positively influence on reducing the environmental accidents. But green health and safety, green orientation and green employee relation are negatively influencing the reduction of environmental accidents in

colleges. So the colleges may arrange regular health checkups for all the employees and can create environmental awareness to reduce the hazardous work environment which in turn reduces the environmental accidents in colleges.

It is found that green health and safety, green employee discipline and green performance evaluation have positive influence on purchase of non-renewable products. It is found that the employee relation and green orientation have negative influence on purchase of renewable products. So the institutions have to create environmental reports for internal assessment of faculty members in the colleges and the pollution prevention programmes have to be arranged for green environment.

It is found that the green health and safety, green orientation and green reward are found to have positive effect on colleges performance of reducing wastes. But the green employee relation and green performance evaluation have negative influence on colleges performance of reducing wastes. So the faculty members have to be self regulated in environmental protection activities of the institution. The recycling of materials has to be practiced effectively in the institution and the reduction in cost of acquiring materials to be ensured.

10. CONCLUSION

This research paper aimed to analyse the influence of GHRM practices on organizational sustainability in colleges at Chittoor District, Andhra Pradesh. The study result revealed that GHRM practices have significantly influenced the sustainability of the colleges. Hence, it is concluded that green human resource management becomes important to provide environmentally friendly products and operations, manage corporate environmental programs successfully and to overcome implementation challenges of corporate environmental programs. Distinguished policies in recruitment, performance appraisal, training and development, employee relations and reward systems are considered powerful tools for aligning employees with a company's environment strategy. Therefore, green human resource management can decisively contribute to successful environmental management.

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